

Promoting the recognition of prior learning in the context of development cooperation: The case of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

In view of the growing importance of the ‘recognition of prior learning’ (RPL) in educational development in lower- and middle-income countries, and of the dearth of research on this new trend, this article presents a study of vocational education and training (VET) in Bangladesh. It examines the evolution of RPL in this country in terms of causal factors and implementation challenges. Based on an analysis of policy documents, practices and qualitative interviews, we develop our argument around Margaret Archer’s model of morphogenetic educational change. The findings suggest that RPL in Bangladesh has grown in the context of considerable general growth in its educational system, but has not been caused by this. More important for RPL’s expansion has been its inclusion in what McGrath calls the “VET policy toolkit”, which donor agencies have started to actively promote in Bangladesh. At the same time, our reading shows that key actors in the development of the country’s VET system have resisted any alterations of the pathways to existing VET qualifications, as they continue to be of the view that access to established VET programmes should be limited to those who have passed eight years of formal schooling (even though many of these graduates still lack solid literacy and numeracy skills). The article argues that global-level actors might need to take such concerns more seriously.

1. Introduction¹

The ‘recognition of prior learning’ (RPL) has become an important element in recent developments in the vocational education and training (VET)² systems of lower and middle income countries (LMICs), reflecting a global trend that also encompasses many comparatively more industrialised countries (ILO, 2018; Council of the European Union, 2012; Cedefop, 2015). While in a few LMICs (South Africa, for instance), RPL has been promoted by national governments as a key element of educational reform (Chisholm et al., 1997), in a larger number of LMICs it was donor-funded VET projects and programmes that promoted RPL schemes, often with the objective of contributing to more equitable

access to VET qualifications, and thus to improved access to employment and income. Yet, despite the growing popularity of RPL in development cooperation, very little research has been dedicated to this topic, be it in regards to its potential effects on improved access to VET, or to the dynamics underlying the design and implementation of RPL schemes. Clearly, more research is needed, also in view of the fact that findings from the literature suggest that RPL in many countries has evolved much more slowly than many policymakers and experts had hoped (Cooper et al., 2017; Harris et al., 2011; Maurer, 2021).

In view of the lack of substantial research on RPL in LMICs, and the fact that the analysis of reforms in education and training needs to strongly take into account underlying societal conditions, the current

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¹ Acronyms used in this article: HSC: Higher Secondary Certificate; ILO: International Labour Organization; LMIC: lower and middle income countries; NPVC: National Pre-Vocational Certificate; NQF: national qualifications framework; NSC: National Skill Certificate; NTVQF: National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework; RPL: recognition of prior learning; SDP: Skills Development Policy; SSC: Secondary School Certificate; TSC: technical schools and colleges; TTC: technical training centre; TVET: technical vocational education and training; USD: United States dollar; VET: vocational education and training; VTI: Vocational Training Institutes.

² There are good arguments both for using either the term vocational education and training (VET) or the term technical vocational education and training (TVET). This text primarily talks about VET, mainly in view of the fact that this is the term increasingly used in the literature. As the term TVET is comparatively more common in Bangladesh (see e.g. Ministry of Education, 2011), we, however, still employ it in a number of quotes from Bangladeshi sources.

article takes a case study approach. It focuses on Bangladesh as a typical case (Seawright and Gerring, 2008, 297) in this regard, given that this country is among the top 6 aid-receiving countries (World Bank, 2021), among which it was the earliest to see the promotion of RPL (Delegation of the European Commission to Bangladesh, 2006). The aim of this article is to contribute to a better understanding of how RPL schemes evolve in LMICs – and why policies sometimes do not meet their objectives in the process of implementation.

The analysis is based on a substantive documentary review of policy and 37 qualitative interviews at the level of policy making and implementation. Data was gathered during different moments that are relevant for this case study – most of it through the main author's fieldwork (approximately 8 months in total) in the years when the RPL policies were being designed (2006–2011), as well as through additional fieldwork (totalling 3 months), coordinated by the two authors in the years 2017–2020.

This article discusses the findings in the light of Margaret Archer's work on the social origins of educational systems, and its reading of the interlinkages of structure and agency in the process of educational expansion (Archer, 1979, 1982), which is contrasted with other theoretical strands in the analysis of education and training systems. Against this backdrop, this study argues that RPL schemes in Bangladesh have hardly improved access to formal VET qualifications, mainly because Bangladesh's key stakeholders in VET (notably the powerful educational administration as well as the VET schools under its control) are critical of alternative pathways to formal VET qualifications. Instead, what we see is the development of donor-driven initiatives that provide access to lowest-level non-formal VET qualifications, which, as of now, have very little value in the labour market and hardly allow for educational mobility.

The main part of this article starts with a review of the literature on RPL, discussing both the concept per se and the various theoretical explanations of its evolution, with a particular focus on how Archer's contributions to comparative education can be applied to the evolution of RPL. It then proceeds to analyse the RPL discourse in international cooperation, an aspect which has, so far, gained very little attention in the literature. The actual case study starts with a discussion of a couple of main trends in the development of education and training in Bangladesh, and then examines the overall VET reforms initiated with donor support from approx. 2005 onwards, the design of the RPL scheme, and the challenges in the implementation process. In the concluding section, a synthesis of the findings from a theoretical perspective points out that although RPL was established in Bangladesh in the context of educational expansion, it was primarily driven by exogenous actors who ultimately had little influence on its implementation – and who didn't take the central reservations of Bangladeshi key stakeholders vis-à-vis RPL seriously enough.

2. Towards a theoretical reading of the expansion of RPL

2.1. RPL as a concept

Recognition of prior learning (RPL) has become a key term in education policy making as well as in the educational research literature (Harris et al., 2011; Bohlinger, 2017). As Bohlinger states, “[recognition] refers to the idea of (publicly) accepting, accrediting and somehow valuing learning results and/or previously received formal qualifications and certificates” (2017, 589). From the outset, a particular focus has been placed on the recognition of results from informal learning that takes place in the workplace or in everyday life (see e.g. Hager, 1998), but also from education and training programmes that are not officially recognised (e.g. non-formal education or programmes followed by migrants in their countries of origins). One of the core aims of RPL is to reduce the need for learners to acquire/prove knowledge and skills several times over, due to a lack of formal alignment between the different learning processes.

There is a very wide literature that documents the considerable variety of RPL schemes, and aims at categorising them (Annen, 2012; Bohlinger, 2017). For the present article, the following two dimensions are of particular relevance:

- *Degree of formality of targeted qualification*: Whereas some RPL approaches enable access to formal qualifications recognised by educational authorities, others lead to non-formal qualifications, e.g. certificates by private bodies. Yet, in many contexts, it is difficult to draw a clear line between formal and non-formal qualifications (see e.g. Affeldt et al., 2017, 15; Brennan, 1997), particularly in view of the fact that (as this article will show) VET qualifications are often offered under the auspices of different public sector agencies (i.e. not only under those of the ministry of education). Formal qualifications are themselves positioned at various education levels: while the focus is often on qualifications in upper secondary VET, there is an increasing number of RPL schemes that provide access to qualifications at lower (e.g. lower secondary) or higher educational levels (e.g. university degrees). An important example of the latter is France (Mathou, 2019).
- *Degree of freedom in the recognition process*: Some of the more liberal approaches to RPL feature a dedicated recognition scheme that is clearly distinct from the regular processes leading to targeted qualifications. Thus, candidates can, for instance, be exempted not only from having to participate in classes but also from all regular exams. Instead, they provide other proofs of competence, e.g. through a portfolio that could include job references and work results or through an evaluation interview (vgl. z.B. Knight, 2006; Fejes and Andersson, 2009). More restrictive RPL schemes insist on RPL candidates having to undergo the same qualifications procedures (e.g. theoretical and practical exams) as regular learners, exempting them only from the regular classes. Typical RPL instruments (e.g. portfolios) may play a role even in restrictive schemes but – in contrast to more liberal schemes – such instruments don't replace the regular qualifications procedures. Such restrictive schemes have also been labelled a “procrustean” approach to RPL (Harris, 1999, 127).

2.2. Literature on the expansion of RPL

While there is a growing body of research on RPL, much of it is dedicated to studying technical aspects, for instance the validity of RPL instruments (e.g. Andersen, 2016; Annen, 2012; Stenlund, 2010; Tuomainen, 2018). Less prominent is the literature interested in the social effects of RPL schemes (e.g. Rothboeck et al., 2018; Schmid et al., 2017). And less prominent still is literature looking at the social dynamics underlying the design and implementation of RPL schemes. Yet, there are, in fact some studies that scrutinise such processes of social change, notably in terms of the role of key actors.

Firstly, the literature suggests that RPL policies have been promoted by policymakers mainly with social policy goals in mind, such as the enhancement of equitable access to qualifications or improvement of access for migrants to labour markets (e.g. Guo, 2014; Singh, 2015). An important example in this regard is the case of South Africa, where post-Apartheid governments considered RPL to be an important way to render education more equitable (e.g. Jansen et al., 2007; Chisholm et al., 1997). At the same time, some authors have also pointed out that policymakers sometimes promote RPL in order to lower public expenditure on education and training – part of a neoliberal education policy agenda –, or in view of economic policy goals (Allais, 2014; Andersson, Fejes & Ahn, 2004; Bagnall, 2000). Even though there is little systematic research in this regard, there is evidence in the literature that policymakers drive RPL under the influence of specific interest groups. Due to the central importance of socio-political arguments for the promotion of RPL, it has been especially trade union circles that have repeatedly advocated RPL, as the examples of France and South Africa show. Indications from Switzerland and Sweden also suggest that employers are

committed to RPL if their industries are affected by a shortage of skilled workers (Maurer, 2019, 2021).

Secondly, even if the literature dealing with RPL in the narrower sense is again quite silent in this regard, there are indications that the simultaneous development of RPL in so many countries might be better explained by taking global or exogenous factors and actors into account. McGrath, 625) (2012) argues that RPL tends to be an integral part of reformist VET policy toolkits worldwide, which have spread in a way that can best be understood as a process of policy diffusion (Chisholm, 2007; Jakobi, 2012). In the comparative education literature, exogenous influencing factors have long been acknowledged, with some focusing more on actors' interests behind global policy borrowing and lending (Steiner-Khamsi, 2004, 2012; Phillips and Ochs, 2003), and others emphasising the importance of a world education culture shaping values and norms in educational policies worldwide (Meyer et al., 1992, 1997). Although these contributions underline the great importance of exogenous factors and actors, they in no way negate the importance of endogenous factors and actors. Some world culture theorists therefore talk about policy-practice decoupling, i.e. about the disconnection between abstract and unrealistic "models of progress and justice" – such as those promoted by donors – and "actual practice" that is in the hands of the countries' existing education and training authorities (Zapp, 2019, 326). How such actual practices are then to be explained, however, is usually not the focus of such contributions.

Thirdly, there is considerable evidence that RPL is, at the level of implementation, not advancing as quickly as many of its proponents would have hoped (Raffe, 2013; Cooper et al., 2017; Maurer, 2019). One important strand of this research points to difficulties that result when actors at the level of implementation see existing quality standards (and the benefits resulting from them) being threatened. In particular, it points to the conflicting objectives of equity and quality and argues that, while equity is a core value at the level of policy making, stakeholders at the level of implementation often do not share these policy goals; they profit from unequal power relations and therefore insist on adhering to traditional measures of quality (Cooper and Harris, 2013; Aarkrog and Wahlgren, 2015; Pitman and Vidovich, 2012; Andersen, 2016; Ismail, 2014).

2.3. RPL from an Archerian perspective

Such findings on the role of key actors in the design and implementation of RPL schemes resonate well with a growing political science approach to the comparative analysis of VET systems, which analyses how struggles around equity and *efficiency* between key actors get resolved in different types of skill formation system (Busemeyer and Trampusch, 2019, 2012; Emmenegger and Seitzl, 2020; Carstensen and Ibsen, 2019). Previous analyses of RPL developments in a number of European countries suggested that RPL was promoted more strongly in statist skill formation systems, where social policy objectives have more weight, and employers have less direct influence, in the formulation of VET policies, than collective or liberal skill formation systems (Maurer, 2019). Yet, as noted elsewhere (Gonon and Maurer, 2012), political economy accounts of skill formation tend to attribute changes in the system mainly to the changes in the wider economic system and the way these changes affect key economic actors; they thereby overlook the fact that growing education systems influence actor dynamics in their own right. For this reason, the present article makes use of Archer's work on the social origins of educational systems and its interpretation of the interlinkages of structure and agency in the process of educational expansion (Archer, 1979, 1982, 1981), which, when it was crafted, was also meant to counter functionalist and neo-Marxist interpretations of educational change and, more recently, has been taken up in other studies of education and training systems in LMICs (Maurer, 2012; Lewin and Little, 1982; Powell and McGrath, 2019).

Arguing from a neo-Weberian, symbolic interactionist framework, Archer regards the process of educational expansion to be the result of a

complex interaction between human agency and social structure. Central to her work on education systems is a morphogenetic model that covers three phases of educational expansion – "take off", "growth" and "inflation" – all of which are shaped by different groups of actors. Of particular relevance to our study is Archer's reading of the growth phase, which is characterised in particular by the increasing social demand for education. This demand results from the fact that educational qualifications start to be seen as a means to access better positions in the labour market. At the same time, those without such qualifications see themselves being increasingly marginalised, which creates political pressure to ease access to education and training. This, in turn, leads to opposition by those who profit from more restrictive access to education; and, if the growth of the education system and the demand from the labour market start to become misaligned, this leads to an inflation of the value of educational qualifications, such that the expansion of the system enters a next phase.

As argued elsewhere, Archer's work, although it draws mostly on European experiences, is of tremendous relevance to other parts of the world too, notably LMICs (Maurer, 2012, 2011). Most importantly, it explains educational expansion in terms of the interests of different groups of actors, rather than 'modernisation' or economic growth (as, for instance, functionalist literature would argue, see e.g. Eisenstadt, 1995). It does not focus on educational expansion as a 'necessary condition' for economic and social change, as argued in the human capital literature (see e.g. Hanushek, 2013) and the global discourse on education and development (see e.g. United Nations, 2015; UNESCO, 2020). Furthermore, and in contrast to comparative education studies that emphasise the critical role of exogenous actors (see also Section 2.2 above), Archer's work reminds us of the critical role of endogenous actors in the educational development of LMICs.

Archer's approach also has considerable potential for the study of social processes underlying the design and implementation of RPL schemes. From this perspective, the simultaneous development of RPL in so many countries can be explained by the fact that different education systems are facing similar challenges, or that the actors who gain importance in the course of educational expansion see RPL as a solution that is in their interest. More specifically, RPL can thus be regarded as a reaction by policymakers to the increasingly pressing fact that growing educational systems penalise individuals who have not undergone a sufficient amount of formal education and training, limiting their ability to participate in society and particularly in the labour market. In the design of RPL schemes, there will then necessarily arise conflicts around the degree to which existing standards of quality should be adapted to improve access to qualifications through RPL. Those who have profited from more restricted access to education will then aim at ensuring that RPL does not lower the barriers to established qualifications in a way that undermines these actors' privileged positions in society and the labour market. As we will see, this approach helps us to theorise the development of RPL in Bangladesh, but it is not in itself sufficient.

3. RPL in international development cooperation

As noted above, RPL can be considered to be an integral part of a VET policy toolkit (McGrath, 2012, 625) and it has therefore become an important element of VET reform in many LMICs, particularly where donor agencies from economically more developed countries are involved. As part of the VET policy toolkit, RPL is often tied to national qualifications frameworks (NQF), which aim to increase the accessibility and permeability of education and training systems, and depend on RPL to make non-formal and informal forms of vocational learning comparable with the more established qualifications (Werquin, 2014; Singh and Duvékot, 2013). The fact that VET programmes are increasingly supposed to be competency-based – giving more weight to practical skills used in the workplace (instead of focusing on knowledge-oriented learning objectives) – makes RPL schemes more relevant in the context of NQFs (Bohlinger, 2008; Parker and Walters, 2008).

As a matter of fact, the rise of RPL (and of NQFs, to which it is often tied) in development cooperation was also a consequence of the fact that VET, from the mid-2000 s onwards, became a priority aid theme, being seen as an important direct means to foster equitable access to employment and income for the poorest (King and Palmer, 2007). This contrasted with earlier decades when VET had been mainly seen as an instrument for economic development, focused more on mid-level occupations (King, 2003; Middleton et al., 1993; Jones, 1997). For development actors who see VET as key to poverty reduction, RPL is obviously attractive, given that it addresses the problem of poorer strata of society having less access to formal education (thus having to learn informally through on-the-job training in a factory, or by way of experience in agriculture or in social care).

Yet, before the concept of RPL entered the development discourse, something similar had evolved in the more industrialised countries: in the US during World War II, and in Canada from the 1980 s (Bohlinger, 2017, 590). One of the first countries that started to promote RPL throughout its education and training system was France, where policymakers from the early 1990 s onwards expected such schemes to support more equitable access to qualifications (Cedefop, 1997). In the developing world, South Africa was among the first to strongly promote RPL – and it was among the first countries worldwide that developed such schemes in the larger context of establishing an NQF (Harris, 1999).

A factor which then considerably contributed to the further diffusion of RPL over the globe was the fact that the European Union, from the mid-1990 s onwards, began to emphasise the importance of lifelong learning and the need to recognise qualifications and skills across country borders (European Commission, 1994). These efforts resulted in its ‘Memorandum on Lifelong Learning’ (European Commission, 2000) as well as the ‘Copenhagen Declaration’, which stated that the development of qualifications frameworks as well as the recognition of qualifications and skills would be important elements of the union’s education and training strategy (European Commission 2002). In 2012, the EU finally provided a number of recommendations to its member countries on how to design and implement RPL schemes (Council of the European Union, 2012). Over the years, the importance of recognising prior learning started also to be emphasised in the EU’s development cooperation strategy (e.g. European Commission, 2014). Given that the EU and its member countries had, collectively, become the world’s largest providers of official development assistance (ODA) (Dearden, 2008), this emphasis added further to the global diffusion of RPL.

Given the growing weight of RPL in development cooperation, an important role was furthermore played by the International Labour Organization (ILO). Already at the International Labour Conference of 2000, its constituents expressed the view that persons “should have the opportunity to have [their] experiences and skills [...] assessed, recognized and certified”, and that “[p]rogrammes to compensate for skill deficits by individuals through increased access to education and training should be made available as part of recognition of prior learning programmes” (ILO, 2000). Yet, the conference clearly had no mandate to formally instruct its member countries to incorporate RPL into their education and training policies. However, as the example of Bangladesh will show, the ILO, in its role as a technical agency with the mandate to implement bi- and multilateral donors’ VET projects, started to play an even more important role as an active promoter of RPL at the level of individual countries (see e.g. Arthur, 2009).

4. Design and implementation of RPL in Bangladesh

4.1. The context: Education and training in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has undergone enormous transformation since its independence from Pakistan in 1971. Devastated by the war and labelled a “basket case” in international politics, the country belonged to the world’s poorest for a number of decades (Alamgir, 2005; World Bank,

1987; Khan, 1984). Having seen considerable economic growth, particularly thanks to the export-oriented manufacturing of garments, Bangladesh today is considered to be a lower middle-income country with a growing middle class. Still, however, it is characterised by strong social inequalities, with a large part of the population living below the poverty line (World Bank, 2016; Sarker et al., 2018).

Both during the colonial period under the British as well as during the Pakistan era, expansion of education in today’s Bangladesh remained slow. Only at independence did educational development become a political priority and an important element of nation building, with the new government and its highly centralised educational administration trying to increase enrolment, notably by nationalising primary schools (Dove, 1983). Enrolment rates began to grow rapidly from 1990, with considerable support from donors. This increase was initially at the primary level (then grades 1–5), and then also at the secondary level (then grades 6–12) (see e.g. World Bank, 1990b; Hossain et al., 2002).

Later, the increase in enrolment rates at the secondary level (grades 6–10) and higher secondary level (grades 11–12) tapered off, with net enrolment rates remaining at about 72% and 36% respectively in 2020; the completion rates also continued to be low at both of these levels, 64% and 79% respectively, in 2020 (BANBEIS, 2020c). Despite the considerable growth of private universities and of a large network of affiliated colleges under the National University, access to tertiary level education remained a particular privilege (BANBEIS, 2020d, 2020a). Accordingly, in 2016/17, only 35% of the working age population was reported to have attained the Secondary School Certificate (SSC, after 10 years of schooling), 7.5% the Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC, after 12 years of schooling) and 4.2% some form of tertiary education qualification (BBS, 2018, 35). Yet, educational qualifications have become important for accessing positions in the small formal segment of the labour market: in 2016/17, 19% of employees in the formal sector had an SSC as their highest qualification, 32% an HSC, and 48.3% a tertiary education qualification (BBS, 2018, 63).

Still, overall, the quality of education has remained low, particularly in relation to foundational skills such as literacy and numeracy, both in general primary and secondary education (MoPME, 2018; Australian Council for Educational Research 2016; CAMPE, 2008). The reasons for low educational quality are a matter of debate, both in the research literature and among policy makers. Some argue that quantitative expansion has come at the cost of quality, e.g., through constant teacher shortages and low per-capita investment in education. In fact, the current teacher-student ratio in secondary schools is 1:40 (BANBEIS, 2020c), while the average annual allocation per student at secondary and tertiary levels, as defined in the state budget, was equivalent to only USD 174 in the 2019/2020 financial year (BANBEIS, 2020b). Others argue that the high level of centralisation of education has also contributed to the deteriorating quality of education, through ineffective teacher allocation and insufficient involvement of local level stakeholders (Choudhury, 2018; Behrman et al., 2002).

It is in this overall context of educational expansion and low educational quality at primary and secondary levels that the development of VET in Bangladesh needs to be analysed. In fact, for many decades, formal VET in today’s Bangladesh remained a very small part of the education system. During the Pakistan period, there were only a few secondary level Vocational Training Institutes (VTI) as well as post-secondary level polytechnics, which were all run under the Ministry of Education (Ministry of Labour and Manpower, 1984, 45 f; Peshkin, 1963). Though the early post-independent governments declared the expansion of VET to be important for the country’s economic development (e.g. Government of Bangladesh, 1974, 29 f) and also promoted the

establishment of practically-oriented short-term courses provided by the Technical Training Centres (TTC) under the Ministry of Labour³ (BMET, 1979), enrolment in VET remained low. The 1980 s even saw a decline in the share of secondary level students enrolled in VET, a trend that was mainly the result of the strong growth of general secondary education (Rafique, 1998, 42; CAMPE, 2006). What is more, in the early 1990 s, the absolute number of students enrolled in VET programmes started to drop (Rafique, 1994, 17). This was, on the one hand, a result of less funding available for VET (see e.g. World Bank, 1990a); on the other hand, however, demand for VET (as in the case of the VTIs) was going down, as it did not open up avenues for educational mobility (Rafique, 1994, 17).

Against this backdrop, and with virtually no support from donors, policymakers in the mid-1990 s decided to vocationalise upper secondary education. They introduced a new vocational stream consisting of two subsequent two-year programmes at the then VTI – one for years 9 and 10 (leading to the Senior Secondary Certificate Vocational (SSC Voc)), and the other for years 11 and 12 (leading to the Higher Secondary Certificate Vocational (HSC Voc)). Enrolment in SSC Voc required students to have completed education up to year 8, and the graduates of the HSC programme were allowed to enter non-university tertiary education programmes (e.g. offered by polytechnic institutes). The introduction of this new programme had the clear objective of contributing to the growth of VET and was based on the insight that, in Bangladesh, social demand for VET would increase if it was better integrated with general education, so that graduates would have an opportunity for educational mobility (Planning Commission, 1995, 141). At the same time, the reform also had the (more implicit) goal of channelling away the growing number of secondary level students from academic secondary education, which was preparing them for entry at the country's universities (Maurer, 2012). In line with Archer's arguments on educational change, the expansion of VET in Bangladesh can thus be attributed not only to economic growth but also to the agency of a "parallelogram of forces (...) with different interests and divergent values" (Archer, 1982, 58).

Soon, SSC and HSC Vocational became Bangladesh's most popular VET programmes (BTEB, 2007), enabled by the fact that not only public Technical Schools and Colleges (TSC) (i.e. the former VTI) but also private TSCs as well as public and private TTCs were allowed to run these programmes. This contributed to the growth of VET enrolment by more than 700% in the years 1999–2017 (BANBEIS, 2018, 2000), resulting in a (fluctuating) 8.5–10.3% share of upper secondary students being enrolled in vocational programmes between 2014 and 2019 (UIS, 2021). Yet, this expansion came at the cost of sometimes very low quality and remoteness from the needs of the world of work, which resulted from a lack of infrastructure and well-trained teachers and trainers (World Bank, 2006; Newaz et al., 2013; Khan, 2019), as well as perpetually poor foundational skills (e.g. in literacy and numeracy) among a substantial proportion of the learners (Australian Council for Educational Research 2016; MoPME, 2018; CAMPE, 2013; World Bank, 2006; Newaz et al., 2013; Khan, 2019). At the same time, both the TSC and the TTC continued to offer training programmes that were shorter and focused more on practical skills (BMET, 2004; BTEB, 2012a). However, all these programmes went on to accept only those learners who had undertaken a minimum of eight years of general education (CAMPE, 2013). The more attractive VET providers admitted students with the best results from general secondary education (see e.g. TSC Sylhet, 2021; CAMPE, 2013).

Yet, access to specific positions in the labour market remained possible without VET qualifications in many cases, as most employers, e.g. in the garment industry, are making hiring decisions based on the

general education levels of job candidates, increasingly valuing educational qualifications at the post-primary level (e.g. grade 8, SSC, HSC, university level) (Kalam and Shimu, 2020; Maurer, 2011, 280; Asian Centre for Development, 2021; Matsuura and Teng, 2020).

4.2. RPL as part of a donor-driven VET reform process

While the strong expansion of the country's VET system from the middle of the 1990 s had been taking place with limited support from multi- and bilateral donors – and in some cases against their explicit advice (Maurer, 2012) – the development of Bangladesh's VET system became a priority theme for donor agencies from approximately 2005 onwards. This was documented by Bangladesh's Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper, which, in expectation of growing multi- and bilateral development assistance, clearly mirrored their aid strategies. In the field of education and training, this strategy paper proposed further expanding VET – which was in line with the governmental policies from the mid-1990 s – and to make it more accessible to those who lacked basic education (Government of Bangladesh, 2005, 134). The latter had, previously, not been a priority of the ministries or other authorities in charge of VET (see e.g. BTEB, 2005).

The most critical intervention in VET that then followed was the Technical and Vocational Education and Training Reform project funded by the European Union. It was implemented by the International Labour Organization (ILO) between 2007 and 2015 and also had considerable impact on the design of VET projects funded by other donors (e.g. by the Asian Development Bank or the World Bank) (Delegation of the European Commission to Bangladesh, 2006; ILO, 2014). This project was also to prove critical because it led to the 2011 Skills Development Policy (SDP) (Ministry of Education, 2011), which, despite not being a formal legal document, was to re-define the key aspects of VET in Bangladesh, in particular its structure and governance. Unsurprisingly, the new policy included many of the elements of what McGrath (2012) labelled the global VET policy toolkit.

At the core of the 2011 SDP lay the ambition to implement a national qualifications framework – later to be called the National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework (NTVQF) – whose functioning was to be detailed in implementation documents based on a global-level blueprint with little reference to the national institutional context (Government of Bangladesh, 2012a, 2012c, 2012d, 2012b, 2013). This framework was thought to bring the VET offers of different ministries under one umbrella, thereby “increasing options for students by broadening program and progression pathways” (Ministry of Education, 2011, 14); to contribute to the design of competency-based curricula, and to ensure that VET would be much more driven by private-sector representatives. Finally, the new policy also introduced the concept of RPL, so that it would be possible to “provide formal recognition of workplace skills obtained in both the formal and informal economies” (Ministry of Education, 2011, 15). The country had hardly any previous experience with RPL (Arthur, 2009, 21), which implies that the evolution of RPL in Bangladesh can clearly be seen as resulting from a donor initiative.

The 2011 SDP also made clear that the main motive for RPL was to promote more equitable access to formal education and training qualifications, as individuals “can enter or re-enter formal training institutions” which would “enhance their employability” (Ministry of Education, 2011, 37). In contrast to other objectives of the new policy (e.g. its ambition to render VET more labour-market oriented), the need for RPL was not justified so much in terms of economic objectives or employers' concerns. Nevertheless, the government emphasised that Bangladesh was “continuing to face skills shortages” and that it was therefore important to open up formal VET to individuals with only informally acquired competencies, so that they could move on to higher qualifications in their respective occupational field (see e.g. Government of Bangladesh, 2015, 14).

³ The denomination of the ministry under which the TTCs have been operating has been subject to regular change. For the sake of readability, we are mainly using the term “Ministry of Labour” for this ministry.

4.3. The design of RPL in the context of the country's qualifications framework

The 2011 SDP also provided an outline of the NTVQF – and the way the framework relates to RPL. Of the 8 skill levels it defined, the two lowest ones were of particular relevance for individuals with “limited general knowledge” and a “very limited range of skills and use of tools required to carry out simple tasks” (Government of Bangladesh, 2013, 11). These are “pre-vocational” levels (pre-voc 1 and 2), leading to the National Pre-Vocation Certificate NPVC 1 and 2, respectively. The introduction of these two levels was in fact revolutionary in the Bangladeshi context, as there had, till then, never been VET qualifications for people who had not completed the full 8 years of primary education. In contrast to existing VET qualifications, however, these pre-vocational qualifications were not meant to prepare individuals for labour market entry, but rather enable them to “pursue formal TVET qualifications” (ILO, 2012, 2).

The pre-vocational levels were followed by five levels dedicated to “vocational education” (NTVQF levels 1–5) as well as by one further level that was reserved for “technical education” (Ministry of Education, 2011, 16). From the perspective of the pre-vocational levels, the first “vocational level” (NTVQF 1) leading to the National Skill Certificate 1 (NSC 1) was of course of particular relevance, as the policy assumed that individuals with a National Pre-Vocation Certificate NPVC 2 would be entitled to continue education and training at this level.

In contrast to qualifications frameworks in many other countries, the 2011 SDP provided no details about how these new levels would relate to existing qualifications. Still, it stated that existing programmes were expected to be revised in order to align with the new framework, so that graduates would receive both the traditional qualification (e.g. SSC voc) and the respective NTVQF certificate (see e.g. Ministry of Education, 2011, 15 & 9). The fact that an official overview by the Government of Bangladesh of the country's VET system made no reference to such existing qualifications (Government of Bangladesh, 2015) is a clear indication that critically important policymakers – and donors – were hoping that these qualifications would no longer be of relevance in the Bangladeshi context and that the NTVQF qualifications would take over that function.

The 2011 SDP furthermore provided details about how individuals would acquire necessary vocational skills at various levels, including at the pre-vocational ones. For these levels, it envisioned that RPL would play a key role, even though it also expected some training centres to come forward and provide structured training programmes. The RPL process which candidates were to undergo in order to achieve a nationally recognised qualification consisted of four main steps, all of which were to be handled by newly established RPL assessment centres (BTEB, 2012b, 4–6): firstly, the candidates were to either submit a portfolio proving their competencies (including appointment letters) or face a challenge test. Secondly, the assessment centres were to screen “potential candidates through a very short interview on basic literacy and numeracy and also knowledge on skills”. Thirdly, the centres were to organise orientation courses of 2–3 days' length, during which they would inform candidates about competency standards, performance criteria as well as about the assessment process, during which they also performed a dummy assessment. Only after these three steps could candidates formally apply. The fourth step was the subsequent assessment, which would use the same assessment tools as applied to students in formal training, conducted by a certified assessor.

4.4. RPL Implementation – and its challenges

Based on the 2011 SDP, different donors (notably the EU, World Bank and ADB) and their implementing organisations started to financially back RPL through their projects. Support was particularly given to further conceptualisation of the administrative and recognition process, the setting up of assessment centres and training of RPL assessors, and

financial support to individuals with an interest in undergoing RPL (Development Technical Consultants, 2016; World Bank, 2019).

After some years, key donors and their implementing organisations were quite satisfied with the effects of the reforms that the government of Bangladesh had initiated with their support (e.g. ILO, 2014). Different evaluations suggest that RPL enabled a high number of individuals to access qualifications (World Bank, 2017; Development Technical Consultants, 2016; ILO, 2017). A study financed by a World Bank project even found evidence of considerable income gains for RPL candidates supported by this project (Development Technical Consultants, 2016). Yet, some reports contended that there remained challenges, notably in terms of the “lack of willingness to follow policy guidelines on TVET” on the part of some government organisations, VET providers and development partners (ILO, 2017, 5).

Our own research suggests that, indeed, a substantial number of individuals reached a qualification through RPL, in particular at the pre-vocational level 2, which leads to the NPVC 2 (BTEB, 2016b). An important reason for this was that, in the first couple of years, there was virtually no regular provision of courses at this level, not least because of a lack of teachers and instructors and because projects had preferred to support the establishment of assessment centres, and the training of assessors, and had provided subsidies to candidates undergoing RPL (BTEB, 2016a; World Bank, 2019). Yet, our field research also suggests that assessment centres were lacking the resources to ensure that all candidates were acquiring the necessary work experience, and then used the “orientation phase” to provide candidates with a skills training in 2–3 days, irrespective of their previous experience. Thus, in the end, the RPL scheme at the pre-vocational level in many cases has taken the form of a short training programme that prepares both the candidates with no work experience and those with considerable experience for a test requiring very low levels of vocational competence.

Furthermore, while the 2011 SDP expected that the NPVC 2, mostly reached through RPL, would be used to access VET programmes at the next higher level of the NTVQF, rather than for labour market entry, the reality was far more complex. The main reason for this was the fact that, as Haolader, Foysool, and Clement, 212) (2017) have noted, “education providers and awarding organisations retain the right to set the entry requirements to individual educational programmes/qualifications” and that “there is no automatic right to progress from one level to the next”. In fact, our review of training programmes leading to an NSC 1 and of their entry requirements shows that only a few of these programmes are accessible to individuals with an NPVC 2. The accessible ones are mostly courses that have been designed in the context of the aforementioned projects, but that do not lead to any of the established vocational qualifications, and therefore lack credibility and social recognition. Some of our interviews furthermore suggest that, even in these courses, the majority of students already have 8 years of primary education (or even SSC, e.g. 10th grade). In contrast, access to the formal VET programmes that had existed before 2011 remains difficult for NPVC 2 holders who have not completed eight years of primary education. This is especially true for the most prominent VET programmes – the SSC (voc) courses – which feature (as noted in Section 4.1) a substantial amount of general education, and prepare students for a highly academic final examination with a 70% pass rate (Aktaruzzaman and Clement, 2011; BTEB, 2019). It is, however, also true for shorter and more practically oriented vocational training courses (of usually 360 h duration) offered under the auspices of both the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Labour (BMET, 2021). In this sense, the aim of the 2011 SDP to use RPL to help individuals lacking finalised primary education to “pursue formal TVET qualifications” (ILO, 2012, 2) has, as of now, clearly not been fulfilled.

In contrast to a World Bank-financed study pointing to considerable income gains by RPL graduates, our qualitative – and therefore not representative – interviews at the level of training centres suggest that such findings might need to be interpreted according to very specific project contexts. In fact, many of our interviewees were rather of the

view that RPL graduates were getting the same jobs that they could have gotten without skills recognition. They also pointed to the possibility that income gains can be realised by individuals who had not been previously employed and lacked work experience. This would also confirm the finding above, that many of the RPL offers did not actually focus on recognising *prior* learning, but rather provided skills training in a very short format that prepared candidates for their assessments.

5. Discussion of the findings in relation to the literature

Our study shows that the *evolution* of Bangladesh's RPL occurred in what Archer, 31, 7) (1982) called the growth phase of the educational expansion process. Nevertheless, the study makes clear that educational expansion did not *directly* trigger RPL, nor had it been particularly driven by endogenous actors pressing for improved access to education and training. In fact, even though educational qualifications have become more important in accessing specific positions in the labour market, VET qualifications play a limited role in this regard. Employers make hiring decisions on the basis of the general education level of job candidates.

Of much more importance were the exogenous actors, notably multi- and bilateral donor agencies and international technical organisations such as the ILO. This is not surprising, taking into account the important role of donors in educational development in LMICs in general and Bangladesh in particular – a topic widely discussed in the literature (Hossain et al., 2002; Adhikary and Lingard, 2018; Meyer et al., 1993; Zapp, 2019). Donors in Bangladesh have thus promoted RPL – as in other parts of the world – as an element of what McGrath, 625) (2012) has labelled a VET policy toolkit, with a view to promoting equitable access to VET and, ultimately, reducing poverty (King and Palmer, 2007). From this perspective, RPL is seen as a means to improve access to VET qualifications for individuals who have acquired skills that are relevant but undocumented, disadvantaging them in the labour market. Clearly, this analysis is based on a reading of interrelations between labour markets and education and training systems in countries where VET qualifications are crucial in the labour market – which is not entirely the case in Bangladesh. In line with world culture theorists, we thus argue that the introduction of RPL policies in Bangladesh was a result of exogenous actors (i.e. bi- and multilateral donors and global technical organisations) pushing instruments shaped by the norms of the global education and training culture. Though this finding is based on a single case study, it is quite certain that such actors play a central role in the establishment of RPL in other LMICs, too.

Our analysis of the *implementation* of RPL in Bangladesh suggests that it did, in fact, contribute to individuals accessing VET qualifications. However, these qualifications were positioned at newly crafted pre-vocational levels with very limited social recognition and value in the labour market. At the same time, the schemes were, in practice, not based on an actual recognition of previously acquired competencies, but were more like a short-term training followed by a test. Furthermore, most graduates of these pre-vocational qualifications were not allowed to enrol in programmes leading to previously existing, more established VET qualifications, as they lacked the necessary eight years of basic education. From a more theoretical perspective, Archer's (1979, 1982) model of morphogenetic educational change offers considerable explanatory power for the analysis of the *implementation* of RPL in Bangladesh: in the current phase of continued strong educational expansion, key actors with control over existing VET qualifications (i.e. the ministries and the other authorities in charge of VET) are critical of reforms that alter access to these qualifications, but are more open to the establishment of qualifications that do not threaten the position of these existing qualifications. As our analysis has shown, donors and their implementing agencies were in no position to make these key actors change existing regulations in a way that would realise the key aim of RPL in Bangladesh – to improve access to existing formal VET qualifications. An important factor is certainly that these key VET actors – even

though they never explicitly expressed political critique at the national level – never fully shared the donors' objective of reorienting VET towards poorer candidates; they continue to be of the view that access to established VET programmes should be limited to those who have passed eight years of formal schooling, though even many of these graduates still lack solid literacy and numeracy skills. For this reason, it would be quite accurate to describe the implementation of RPL in Bangladesh as a case of policy-practice decoupling (Zapp, 2019, 326).

6. Concluding remarks in view of theory building and policymaking

Overall, this study adds to the current literature on educational development by demonstrating that Archer's (1979, 1982) argument about the critical role of different interest groups and institutions in shaping the development of education systems applies not just in European countries, but also in LMICs (Maurer, 2012, 2011). It argues that, notwithstanding the enormous influence of international donors in the formulation of education policy goals in LMICs, the actual processes of educational change can only be understood by analysing the agency of endogenous actors. With respect to the growing literature on RPL, this article is one of the few papers that analyses the social conditions that have shaped the formulation of RPL policy in an LMIC, and the challenges of implementation, reaffirming the general finding that RPL policy implementation always tends to involve numerous difficult challenges (Cooper et al., 2017; Harris et al., 2011; Maurer, 2021, 2019).

Nevertheless, RPL will continue to be a common element of the global VET toolkit, as it is very much in line with donors' understanding that VET needs to be made more accessible to the poor. RPL is thus very similar to 'qualifications frameworks', which – despite very limited evidence of their effectiveness – have similarly spread across the globe (e.g. Allais, 2014, 2017; Raffe, 2013). In this context, it should also be recognised that RPL must not lead to a weakening of existing VET programmes. To achieve the overarching goals in VET, the resistance of key education stakeholders to altering access to VET qualifications, for example for learners without sufficient foundational skills (e.g. numeracy and literacy), should actually be taken seriously.

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